

**STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF COMMUNICATION SKILL PROGRAM IN ENGLISH
FOR B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS.**

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Abstract

Quality education is the aim of present education. Today in the era where students are given right to take education, it is our duty and responsibility to provide them quality education. Such education can be given through many ways and through teaching various subjects using new techniques.

Researches are one of the way to provide quality education. Here in this paper researcher deals with how a particular research help teachers to enhance quality of English language education.

In the present paper researcher tends to study effectiveness of communication skill program which was prepared by the researcher. To study this effectiveness the researcher has done experiment on B.Ed. students having English method. Data was collected using achievement test, observation diary and students feedbacks. After collection of data researcher has done both quantitative using graphs and qualitative data analysis using quantifications and finally research conclusions were made.

Key words: *Quality Education, English communication skill, B.Ed. students.*

1. Introduction

“The language teacher must be educated at least to the level of his peers. He must have a general preparation of a teacher. (He)must know the target language well enough to be imitated by his students.”

Robert Lado

The present research aims to study effectiveness of communication skill program in English for B.Ed. students.

Teacher teach as they are taught not as they are told to teach so they must be taught/trained properly to teach skill based and learner centered curriculum of English subject.

Teacher occupies a pivotal position in education it is important to have the right English teachers who are fully equipped to do justice to the English language education. Teacher must be acquainted with the latest techniques of language teaching and should also have knowledge of phonetics. To have such teachers, efforts must be taken from pre service training i.e. B.Ed. course.

But B.Ed. course syllabus of English method does not have any provision to enhance language skills. This is the reason why the researcher thinks that extra efforts must be taken to make would be teachers of English better equipped and competent. Researcher has prepared communication skill program which will help student teachers to enhance communication skill. Researcher hopes this research will definitely help to provide **Quality Education**.

2. Objectives

- To prepare English communication skill programme for enhancement of English communication skill of B.Ed. students.
- To study effectiveness of English communication skill programme

3. Research methodology

Experimental method has been applied for the present investigation, which has been carried out by administering experiment on B.Ed. students.

4. Sample, Design and Research tool

In this study it was decided to carry out an experiment on 15 students of B.Ed. course having English method.

For the present experimental research 'Pretest posttest single group design' was used.

Achievement test (Which was used as pre and post test), observation diary and students feedbacks were tools of data collection.

5. Procedure

- Preparation of achievement test
- Preparation of communication skill program
- Administration of pretest
- Implementation of programme
- Post tests
- Data analysis and interpretation
- Conclusion.

6. Limitations

- The present research is restricted to B.Ed. students of Marathi medium having English method.
- The present research concern with one aspect of language skills (LSRW) i.e. communication skill.

7. Data collection

- In the present research quantitative data was collected by using achievement test

- Quantitative data was collected by maintaining observation diary and students feedbacks.

8. Data analysis

Quantitative data analysis

Marks obtain in communication skill tests were as further:

Communication skill mark lists		
Sr. No.	Pretest Total out of 50	Posttest Total out of 50
1	18	45
2	24	45
3	15	44
4	17	46
5	28	49
6	27	49
7	25	49
8	14	44
9	12	43
10	27	47
11	12	42
12	24	47
13	15	46
14	18	42
15	17	40

Graphical representation of data

Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative analysis of data collected by observation diary was done by using quantification is as follows:

Numbers in brackets indicates frequency of student teachers

Observations during speaking skill pretest Q.1 Speech on one topic

- Students were looking confident while communication. (5)
- Students were not accurate but fluent. (3)
- Students were accurate and fluent. (2)
- Students could not speak even a single line confidently. (10)
- Students could not speak a single grammatically correct sentence. (13)
- Students feel frightened and uneasy to speak in English
- Students have impact of mother tongue. (8)

Observations during pretest Q.2 Say dialogues for following situations.

- Students express confidently with expression but constructions were wrong. (5)
- Students could not find words to express. (5)
- Students were hesitating. (8)
- Students spoke wrong constructions. (10)
- Students were communication without any expression on their faces, rather they were confused. (10)

Conclusions:

- Students were not confident.
- Students don't know how construction expressions for communication.
- Students have less vocabulary.

Observations during speaking skill orientation.

- Students were eager to know about speaking skill, vowels diphthongs and their articulation. (12)
- Students Showed interest in speech act theory
- Students tried to make sounds using knowledge of articulation.
- Students on their own sit face to face and took help of their friends in their practice.
- Students tried to avoid impact of mother tongue by practicing articulation.

Observations during pre communicative activities to develop fluency or command on linguistic system.

- Students tried carefully to understand the place of articulation of all alphabets and vowels. (12)
- Students were first hesitating to take part in pronunciation drill. (13)
- Further they took interest and tried to pronounce words. (15)
- It helps to build confidence in them.(15)

- In the last phase of drilling all have willingly taken parting drill without hesitation. (15)
- Students having impact of mother tongue find it difficult to pronounce words.(5)
- They took more efforts in the class and also at home. (5)
- Students took help of their friends in learning pronunciation.(10)
- Students find difficult to pronounce /f/ sound. (1)
- Student find difficult to pronounce diphthongs but took efforts to learn pronunciation.(10)
- Students sat face to face and learn pronunciation until they learn. (15)
- Students ask for more time to learn pronunciation.(10)
- Students said, “We will give more time for pronunciation drill because this is basic ability for communication skill. (8) Others were agreeing with them.

Conclusions:

- Students realize importance of pronunciation drill so they were careful.
- Students realize that more practice will help them to be perfect so they were serious about practice and promise to do it at home also.
- Practice help to build confidence in them, this confidence leads them in practicing pronunciations without hesitation and to master them.

Observations during Activity – word drill.

- Students tried carefully to understand what word accent is.
- Students enjoyed bi- syllabic, tri- syllabic and monosyllabic words.
- They have created rhythm in those words; they have started enjoying melody of English language which has rhythms.
- They told the researcher that mono syllabic words were more rhythmic.

Conclusions:

- Activity about accents help students understand that English language is different from Indian languages it has its own characteristics and it should be learn without interference of mother tongue.

Observations during Activity – Accent in connected speech & rhythm.

- Students understand accents in sentences, they carefully understand what is rhythm and how does it work.
- They practice sentences and started saying these sentences again and again.
- They enjoyed rhythm in sentences.
- They ask to give more sentences for practice.
- Students brought many sentences from many sources and practice them in the class.

Conclusions:

- Students realize importance of practice; they practice more until they master the accent.

Observations during Activity – falling, rising and falling rising intonation.

- Students understand carefully where these tones were used.
- Students first decide whether the sentence is statement, command, question, incomplete utterance or special implicate and then pronounce it correctly.
- Students were enjoying pronouncing sentences.
- They pronounce sentences correctly using falling rising intonation.
- They practice sentences and started saying these sentences again and again.

Observations during speaking skill posttest Q.1 Speech on one topic.

- Students were looking confident while communication. (15)
- Students were trying to be accurate and fluent.(15)
- Students could easily speak in English for three minutes.(15)
- Their sentences were grammatically correct.(15)
- Vocabulary used was good.(15)
- They tried to avoid impact of mother tongue and use received pronunciations
- without hesitation.(15)
- Their expressions gestures were proper.(15)
- There was speech clarity and content relevance in their Speech. (15)

Observations during post test Q.2 Say dialogues for following situations.

- Students express confidently with expression and gestures.(15)
- Students could use ample vocabulary to express.(15)
- They were not hesitating to take turns in the conversations.(15)
- Their contents were relevant to the topics. (15)
- There was speech clarity and confidence in their utterances. (15)
- Students have started using intonation patterns in their statements, questions, requests, commands, and exclamations

Analysis of students' feedbacks about communication skill programme

- Communication skill orientation makes them know the mechanism of skill, articulation stress and intonation which was new for them
- Communication skill activities and practice help to develop not only communication ability but also the ability to interact or communicate in English. (7)
- Students find easy to speak on certain topics confidently. (10)

- Students mentioned that they can take part in the conversation. (8)
- They mentioned that they need more activities to develop their vocabulary.(6)
- Students tell the researcher that the grammar taught during the programme (tenses, indirect speech, active and passive construction etc.), help them to construct sentences. (12)
- Students also mentioned that this programme develop confidence to take part in the conversation in any situation. Hereafter they will be able to face situations where English communication necessary. (15)

9. Conclusions of the research

- 86% Students have got more than 20 marks out of 25.(13)
- 13% Students have got 20 marks out of 25.(2)
- Communication activities helped Students to developed confidence and communicative competencies.
- Communication activities helped them to use their passive vocabulary actively.
- These activities help students to enhance communication skill.
- This programme will definitely help to give quality education.

10. Directions for further studies

- Such study can be done to enhance other language skills such as listening, communication, reading, writing, interacting, conversation etc.
- Such study can be done to enhance language skills of students of primary, secondary, or any other level.
- It can also be done to enhance language skills of other languages such as Hindi.

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